

Progress in fast-timing Ce-doped garnet scintillators by complex codoping with divalent cations

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Abstract

This work focuses on the development of fast-timing inorganic scintillators for use in cutting-edge particle physics experiments at colliders and time-of-flight positron emission tomography (TOF-PET). Significant progress in enhancing the timing performance of $Y_3Al_5O_{12}$ (YAG) scintillators is reported, achieved by optimizing the co-doping conditions with Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} . The optimized crystals exhibit fast rise and decay times of 30 ps and 26 ns, respectively, alongside an impressive coincidence time resolution (CTR) of 131 ps, while maintaining a high light output of over 22,000 ph/MeV. The incorporation of dopants into the YAG lattice is explored, providing insights into the mechanisms driving scintillation response in YAG:Ce,Ca,Mg crystals. Furthermore, uniformity in scintillation properties was demonstrated along a large, 120 mm-long YAG:Ce,Ca,Mg ingot, which was grown using the Czochralski method in a tungsten crucible.

Keywords: Scintillator; light output; decay constant; codoping; electromagnetic calorimeter

1. Introduction

Ongoing preparations of experiments at future colliders such as High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC) in CERN involve the selection of appropriate scintillation materials capable to withstand increased radiation loads and distinguish high frequency (25 ns^{-1}) particle collision events [1]. The electromagnetic calorimeter (ECAL) upgrade II of LHCb experiment at the future HL-LHC involves substitution of plastic by inorganic scintillators in the central part of the detector where the radiation doses of up to 1 MGy are expected [2]. This inner region should comprise a spaghetti calorimeter (SPACAL-W), composed of 40 modules of scintillating crystal fibres, each consisting of 81 fibres embedded into W absorber [3]. Such construction requires less crystalline material compared to monolithic bulk crystals, provides possibility to use crystalline materials with moderate Z_{eff} and density, as W may attenuate most of a particle energy. Furthermore, different types of fibres can be combined with various sampling fractions, for instance, Cherenkov radiators, scintillators, neutron-sensitive materials [3].

According to modelling predictions [4], considering the given frequency of particle collisions, a scintillator decay time should not exceed 15 ns while a light output should be at least 10000 – 15000 ph/MeV with a low afterglow to avoid pileup and distinguish sequential collision events. In parallel, development of Positron emission tomography (PET) technologies involving time of flight (TOF) approach requires inorganic scintillators with a high coincidence time resolution (CTR) below 100 ps, which can be achieved at combination of a high light output with very fast rise/decay times of a scintillation pulse [5, 6].

Ce-doped garnet scintillators such as $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ (YAG), $\text{Lu}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ (LuAG), $\text{Gd}_3(\text{Al,Ga})_5\text{O}_{12}$ (GAGG) are among the candidates for SPACAL-W. These materials are well-known for their moderate-to-high density and Z_{eff} , a high light yield and radiation hardness, convenient emission range in the green part of the spectrum [7]. Ce^{3+} activator ions replace large trivalent rare earth cations in dodecahedral sites of garnet lattice, while octahedral and tetrahedral sites are filled with Al^{3+} or Ga^{3+} with smaller ionic radii. A high isomorphic capacity of the garnet lattice allows for substitution in all the three cation crystallographic sites, providing a variety of host compositions. Substitution of host cations affects the energy structure of crystals, especially the location of the ground and excited levels of activator ions and traps in the bandgap, and, as a consequence,

scintillation properties [8]. Meanwhile, Ce-doped garnets exhibit a relatively slow scintillation decay compared to other Ce-doped scintillators. This is attributed to the Ce^{3+} intrinsic radiation lifetime of approximately 50-60 ns in the rare earth garnet hosts [9]. Furthermore, Ce-doped garnets possess long components of scintillation decay owing to carrier trapping on intrinsic defects, such as antisites (rare earth ion occupying octahedral sites) and oxygen vacancies [10].

This means that Ce^{3+} scintillation decay time in rare earth garnets time may be reduced below the Ce^{3+} intrinsic lifetime only by luminescence quenching, sacrificing light output. Hence most of the works on fast-timing garnets were focused on GAGG:Ce, the brightest garnet scintillator with a light output approaching 60000 phot/MeV [11], where a reasonable light yield is assumed to retain even after partial quenching. Luminescence quenching can be achieved by codoping with divalent alkaline earth cations promoting partial transfer of Ce^{3+} into tetravalent state. Energy levels of Ce^{4+} are located closer to the conductance band edge, competing for electron capture with shallow traps, thus improving electron transfer to Ce^{3+} luminescence centers [12, 13]. Meanwhile, smaller energy gap between the Ce^{4+} energy levels states and the conductance band edge promotes thermal ionization from the Ce^{4+} 5d levels to the conductance band thus decreasing scintillation decay time below the Ce^{3+} intrinsic lifetime [12, 13]. Furthermore, the coexistence of Ce^{3+} and Ce^{4+} accelerates the scintillation process reportedly by eliminating the time spent on hole diffusion to stable Ce^{4+} before it captures an electron from the conductance band and transfers to a metastable Ce^{3+} state with subsequent radiative electronic transition from 5d to 4f energy levels [12-14].

Doping by alkali earth divalent atoms to control $\text{Ce}^{3+}/\text{Ce}^{4+}$ ratio was addressed in many works, see, for example, [12-16]. Systematic studies on the impact of different divalent cations on scintillation parameters of Ce-doped garnets were performed in [17, 18]. Most valuable results were demonstrated with Mg^{2+} . The effective decay time at Mg-codoping in GAGG:Ce calculated based on the contribution of three decay components fell to 0.7 ns, while the light output was quenched to several hundred ph/MeV [19]. Codoping of YAG:Ce by up to 2% of Mg resulted and the enhancement of light output by ca. 25%, decrease of the afterglow level by an order of magnitude, decrease of decay time from 117 to 85 ns [20]. Meanwhile, heavy doping of LuAG:Ce [12] by Mg resulted in a huge loss in light output down to few hundred – few thousand ph/MeV.

Similar effects were observed at garnet doping with Ca^{2+} ions. The acceleration of the main decay component to 27 ns (with $\tau_{eff} = 35$ ns) was registered in GAGG:Ce,Ca along with deterioration of

the light output to 14800 ph/MeV [14]. Doping of YAG:Ce with up to 1% Ca decreased the time of the main decay component to 50 ns [16]. Our systematic study on YAG:Ce codoped with divalent cations [18] qualitatively confirmed the data of [16], with the main decay time of 55 ns and the contribution of slow decay components within 4% in Ca²⁺-codoped in YAG:Ce.

Summarizing, codoping solely with Ca²⁺ or Mg²⁺ has not resolved the tradeoff between short decay time and high light output: the decay time was too slow or/and scintillation yield was negligible. Note that scintillation decay in YAG:Ce was the slowest among the studied garnets, with or without codoping with Ca²⁺ or Mg²⁺. Meanwhile, recent paper by Huang et al. [21] has demonstrated that the main decay time of GAGG:Ce ceramics codoped with equal concentrations of Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ was 31 ns, remarkably shorter against 40 and 42 ns in the Mg²⁺ or Ca²⁺-codoped samples, respectively, although Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ concentrations were not optimized. Basing on the highest intensity of the Ce⁴⁺-O²⁻ CT absorption band in the dual-codoped crystal, “synergetic effect” of Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ on accelerated luminescence decay was attributed to a higher Ce⁴⁺ fraction.

Cost is another key indicator of scintillator usability. Prices of Ir crucibles, which are necessary to grow large GAGG:Ce and other Ga-containing crystals, have skyrocketed in the last decade. The attempts to substitute Ga³⁺ with Sc³⁺ enabling crystal growth in Mo or W crucibles were not successful as Sc³⁺ forms deep traps, which degrade scintillation performance of Gd₃Al_{5-x}Sc_xO₁₂:Ce (GASG:Ce) [22]. As alternative to GASG:Ce, we have proposed YAG:Ce, which can be grown in cheap W crucibles [23]: recently we have demonstrated a very high light output of approximately 30000 ph/MeV and timing parameters similar to GAGG:Ce [24]. The only remarkable difference is the density, which is 6.7 g cm⁻³ in GAGG:Ce and 4.4 g cm⁻³ in YAG:Ce that may call a need for longer crystalline elements to attenuate high energy particles. However, this should not be a critical issue, as most of particle energy in SPACAL-W may be absorbed by a tungsten matrix.

This work reports the first time growth of triple-codoped YAG:Ce,Ca,Mg crystals by the Czochralski method. Following the promising results on GAGG:Ce,Ca,Mg ceramics [21] the impact of double codoping by Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ on performance of YAG:Ce host was verified. A significant progress has been achieved in the timing characteristics of YAG:Ce,Ca,Mg due to the optimization of the co-doping conditions. We also discuss possible factors affecting scintillation performance at such doping.

2. Methods

2.1. Sample preparation

Y_2O_3 , Al_2O_3 , CeO_2 , MgO , CaO raw materials (4N, Shenzhen Nexconn Pharmatechs) calcined at $800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in air were loaded into W crucibles in stoichiometric composition without preliminary solid-state synthesis. Crystals were grown by the Czochralski method in W crucibles in $\text{Ar}+\text{CO}$ atmosphere. The typical crystal size was 15-20 mm dia. and a length of up to 50 mm. Growth conditions were described in detail elsewhere [23]. The first set of $\text{YAG}:\text{Ce},\text{Ca},\text{Mg}$ crystals (YAG1-7) contained 1 at% Ce, which was the optimal one in terms of light output [24]. The $\text{Ca}+\text{Mg}$ doping concentration was kept at 1%, equal to Ce concentration, while Ca/Mg ratio varied from 1:4 to 4:1. The second set of $\text{YAG}:\text{Ce},\text{Ca},\text{Mg}$ crystals (YAG14-19) with the increased content of the divalent codopants with the $\text{Ca}+\text{Mg}/\text{Ce}$ ratios from 1:1 to 3:1 samples was grown from the melt by the same procedure. All the mentioned concentrations relate to those in the melt, unless stated otherwise.

Fig. 1. A set of $2 \times 2 \times 3\text{ mm}^3$ $\text{YAG}:\text{Ce},\text{Ca},\text{Mg}$ samples with increasing $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{Mg}^{2+}$ ratio from left to right before (above) and after (below) thermal annealing.

Crystalline samples of $5 \times 5 \times 2\text{ mm}^3$ dimensions were cut for the measurements of optical absorption, excitation and luminescence spectra, light output and scintillation decay times. A set

of 2x2x3 mm³ samples was fabricated for determination of CTR. All the samples were annealed in air at 1600 °C. As one can see (Fig. 1), the samples were remarkably bleached after annealing, especially Ca-rich samples. The compositions of the studied samples are summarized in Table 1. YAG:Ce and YAG:Ce,Ca crystals used for comparison were obtained in the works [18, 24] in the same conditions.

Table 1. Melt compositions at crystal growth by the Czochralski method. The samples are arranged not by consecutive number, but in a sequence with changing Ca/Mg or Ce/Ca+Mg ratios (marked with bold).

Sample no.	Ce, at%	Ca, at. %	Mg, at. %	Ca/Mg	Ce/(Ca+Mg)
Adjusting Ca/Mg ratio					
YAG6	1	-	1	-	1:1
YAG7	1	0.25	1	1:4	1:1
YAG3	1	0.25	0.75	1:3	1:1
YAG1	1	0.5	0.5	1:1	1:1
YAG2	1	0.75	0.25	3:1	1:1
YAG5	1	1	0.25	4:1	1:1.25
Adjusting Ce/Ca+Mg ratio					
YAG18	1.5	1.12	0.38	3:1	1:1
YAG19	1	1	0.25	4:1	1:1.25
YAG16	1	1	0.33	3:1	1:1.33
YAG17	1	1.5	0.5	3:1	1:2
YAG15	0.5	0.75	0.25	3:1	1:2
YAG14	0.3	0.75	0.25	3:1	1:3

2.2.Characterization

2.1 Absorption and wavelength resolved luminescence

The absorption spectra of the samples tested were measured using a PerkinElmer LAMBDA 650 UV/VIS spectrometer. The instrument provided with a deuterium and halogen lamp and covers the wavelength range of 190 to 900 nm. The light passes through a monochromator and then split into two branches. One of the monochromatic light beams, whose intensity can be tuned by means of an iris, traverses the crystal sample placed on a moving stage. The other beam is instead employed to monitor instrumentation drift during the acquisition. Both beams were focalized through a photomultiplier measuring their intensity.

The photoluminescence spectra as well as the photoluminescence excitation spectra of crystals were measured with Perkin Elmer LS55 automatic spectrofluorimeter. The spectrofluorimeter emits a tunable monochromatic beam of light onto a sample and measures the intensity of luminescence as a function of its wavelength.

2.2. Light output and scintillation decay

The pulse-height spectra of the samples were measured using setup consisted of a Hamamatsu R2059 PMT placed in a dark box at 18 °C, analog attenuator and DT5720 CAEN digitizer working in charge integration mode. The PMT is biased at 2500 V, providing sufficient gain to resolve the charge of single photoelectron pulses. That allows to convert the total charge of a scintillation event to photoelectrons produced. The number of photons impinging on the PMT is obtained correcting for the average quantum efficiency of the PMT, computed as the weighted average of the scintillator's emission and the PMT's quantum efficiency. The crystals were placed directly to input window of PMT with Rhodorsil grease coupling and Teflon wrapping to maximize light collection. The ^{137}Cs (662 keV) gamma radioactive source was used for excitation of scintillations. The whole setup was enclosed in a temperature controlled black box. The PMT is biased at 2500 V, providing sufficient gain to resolve the charge of single photoelectron pulses. That allows to convert the total charge of a scintillation event to photoelectrons produced. The number of photons impinging on the PMT is obtained correcting for the quantum efficiency of the PMT, convolved with the emission spectra of the samples.

The scintillation decay curves were measured using a Time Correlated Single Photon Counting (TCSPC) setup. A pulse diode laser (Pico-Quant, PDL 800-B) was used as an excitation source of an X-ray tube XRT N5084 from Hamamatsu. It generated an X-ray beam with a continuous energy

spectrum between 0 and 40 keV (with a ≈ 10 keV mean energy). The beam, after crossing a brass collimator, was focused on the tested sample and its scintillation light was collected using a hybrid photomultiplier (HPM 100-07 Becker Hickl) working in TCSPC mode. A 420 nm long pass filter was placed in front of the hybrid photomultiplier to suppress air excitation contribution to the emission distributions. The measurements were done hitting the sample on one surface and detecting the emitted light from the same surface (reflection mode). The signal of the hybrid PMT was then fed to an amplifier and timing discriminator and was then used as the stop signal of a time to digital converter, while the start was provided by an external trigger of the pulse diode laser. Scintillation time profile for each sample was mathematically described with a multi-exponential function:

$$f(t | \theta) = \sum_{i=1}^3 \rho_i \cdot \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{t-\theta}{\tau_{d,i}}\right) - \exp\left(-\frac{t-\theta}{\tau_{r,i}}\right)}{\tau_{d,i} - \tau_{r,i}} \cdot \Theta(t - \theta) + \varepsilon$$

where $\tau_{r,i}$ and $\tau_{d,i}$ are the i -th components of the rise and decay time constants respectively, while ρ_i is the weight of the i -th component, θ is the instant above which the scintillation pulse starts and ε is the background. The scintillation pulse function defined above was then convoluted with the impulse response function (IRF) of the setup (≈ 180 ps FWHM) to fit the decay spectra obtained. The effective decay time was defined as:

$$\frac{1}{\tau_{d,\text{eff}}} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{A_i}{\tau_{d,i}}$$

2.3. Coincidence Time Resolution

The coincidence time resolution (CTR) is defined as the resolution of the difference in detection time of two 511 keV back-to-back gamma photons produced by a ^{22}Na source. The CTR of some of $2 \times 2 \times 3$ mm³ YAG samples were measured at CERN with dedicated setup based on the NINO ASIC and is described in detail in [25]. A ^{22}Na source was placed between the sample under test and a reference $2 \times 2 \times 3$ mm³ LYSO:Ce pixel wrapped with several layers of Teflon and coupled to a HPK S13360-3050PE SiPM with Cargille Meltmount optical glue. The tested crystal was wrapped with Teflon and coupled with Rhodorsil optical grease to another HPK S13360-3050PE SiPM. The signals of SiPMs were split into two, with one branch fed into the NINO ASIC, whose leading edge delay was the timestamp of the channel, and the other used to measure the energy

deposit. Only photopeak events were selected for the measurement. The pulses were digitized with a DRS4 board, 5 GS/s, bandwidth 700 MHz. The histogram of the mutual time delay was produced and fitted with a Gaussian function and its full width at half maximum (FWHM), once corrected for the reference (77 ± 2 ps FWHM), was the contribution of the crystal measured. This, multiplied by $\sqrt{2}$ in the assumption of two identical crystals, is the resulting CTR. For each sample a threshold scan was performed to find the optimal settings.

3. Results

3.1 Adjusting Ca/Mg ratio in YAG:Ce,Ca,Mg

Depending on the concentration and type of the codopant, the intensities of the Ce^{3+} 4f-5d₁ absorption band peaked around 470 nm and the Ce^{4+} -O²⁻ charge transfer (CT) band <350 nm in the spectra varied significantly in the absorption spectra (Fig. 2a). Remarkably, the Ce^{3+} absorption band weakens with Ca^{2+} addition, but, in contrast to many previous reports on Ce-doped garnets [13, 17, 19, 20], it reinforces at Mg^{2+} -codoping. The weakest Ce^{3+} absorption peak is observed at Ca^{2+} concentration of 0.75 %, and at 1% Ca it is completely unresolved. Assuming that all cerium is in trivalent state in YAG:Ce without codoping and the linearity between the amount of trivalent cerium and the intensity of Ce^{3+} absorption peak at 470 nm, one may evaluate the ratio of Ce^{3+} remaining in the crystals. For instance, comparing the YAG2 sample with $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{Mg}^{2+}$ concentrations of 0.75%/0.25% with the YAG:Ce etalon, approximately 4% of cerium remains in the stable trivalent state at such codoping. The CT band intensity increases both at Mg^{2+} - and Ca^{2+} -codoping, more remarkably in the latter case. Meanwhile, a wide unstructured absorption was revealed at >350 nm in all the measured spectral range at 1% Ca, probably, attributed to a large number of scattering centers in the crystal. Note that the latter sample was inhomogeneous (see YAG5 sample in Fig. 1) involving the regions of different color.

Luminescence excitation and emission spectra of the obtained crystals are typical for Ce^{3+} -doped garnets with the main excitation bands at 470 and 340 nm corresponding to 4f-5d_{1,2} transitions (Fig. 2b). As the intensity of the strongest band Ce^{3+} absorption band around 470 nm was too high, the relative change in excitation efficiency may be evaluated by the intensity of the 340 nm band. The intensity rises as Mg^{2+} concentration increases and weakens as Ca^{2+} content increases,

confirming the trends in the absorption spectra (see Fig. 3a). Photoluminescence spectra are very similar in shape (Fig. 2c).

Fig. 2. Optical properties of YAG:Ce,Ca,Mg with various $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{Mg}^{2+}$ ratios in comparison with YAG:Ce etalon: (a) absorption spectra; (b) normalized luminescence excitation spectra; (c) luminescence spectra.

The light output gradually decreased with the increasing Ca/Mg ratio, however, remaining over 20000 ph/MeV in all the Ca-Mg-codoped samples. The scintillation decay accelerated with Ca^{2+}

content (Fig. 3), but the trend for effective decay time, τ_{eff} was not monotonous, with the fastest decay in the YAG2 and YAG5 crystals at the Ca/Mg ratios of 3:1 and 4:1, respectively. The fastest rise time τ_{rise} and τ_{eff} were observed in YAG2 – 30 ps and 26 ns, respectively, yielding a CTR of 131 ps FWHM (see Fig. 3c,d). Remarkably, the decay decelerated in YAG:Ce,Ca sample, so Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} must coexist to provide a faster rise/decay constants. This result confirms the reported [21] synergy between Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} . All the scintillation parameters including rise times and CTR are summarized in Table 2.

Fig. 3. Scintillation parameters of YAG:Ce,Ca,Mg with various Ca/Mg ratios: (a) decay curves at X-ray excitation; (b) pulse-height spectra under 662 keV γ -rays, (c) dependence of light output and decay time on Ca/Mg ratio, and dependence of CTR on NINO threshold in YAG2 (d).

3.2. Adjusting Ce and codopant concentrations in YAG:Ce,Ca,Mg

Summarizing the data on light output and decay times obtained in the previous section, it is obvious that dual Ca^{2+} - Mg^{2+} codoping provides remarkably better combination of light output and decay constant compared to $\text{YAG}:\text{Ce}$ (see Table 2). However, with the introduced doping concentrations in $\text{YAG}:\text{Ce},\text{Ca},\text{Mg}$ we have not succeed in reducing the decay constant below 26 ns. Meanwhile, photoluminescence decay was accelerated to few ns in heavily-doped $\text{GAGG}:\text{Ce},\text{Mg}$ due to the decreased energy barrier for thermal quenching of $5d_1$ Ce^{3+} excited state in closely spaced ($\text{Ce}-\text{Mg}$) pairs [26], while the decay times even below 1 ns were registered under X-ray excitation [19]. Following these results, we produced a set of $\text{YAG}:\text{Ce},\text{Ca},\text{Mg}$ samples with the increasing concentration of the divalent codopants, namely increasing the $(\text{Ca}+\text{Mg})/\text{Ce}$ ratio from 1:1 to 3:1 (samples YAG14-19), while preserving the optimal $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{Mg}^{2+}$ ratios of 3:1 or 4:1 (see Table 2).

Fig. 4. Optical parameters of $\text{YAG}:\text{Ce},\text{Ca},\text{Mg}$ crystals with various $\text{Ce}/(\text{Ca}+\text{Mg})$ ratios: (a) absorption spectra, (b) Ce^{3+} luminescence excitation spectra, (c) Ce^{3+} luminescence spectra.

a

b

Fig. 5. Scintillation properties of YAG:Ce,Ca,Mg with various Ce/(Ca+Mg) ratios: (a) scintillation decay curves; (b) pulse-height spectra.

In contrast to the first set of the samples (YAG1-7), all the absorption spectra in the second set contain a weak or unresolved 4f-5d₁ Ce³⁺ band at 460 nm, a strong charge transfer band of O²⁻ - Ce⁴⁺ complex, and a strong background absorption correlating with the Ca²⁺ content (Fig. 4a). The

strongest Ce^{3+} bands in the luminescence excitation spectra (Fig. 4b) were registered in YAG17 and YAG18 containing the highest Mg^{2+} concentration. These samples have also the strongest long-wavelength shoulder of luminescence band (Fig. 4c).

The $\text{Ce}/(\text{Ca}+\text{Mg})$ variation has not provided a τ_{eff} acceleration as the latter remained in the range of 30-33 ns, whereas τ_{eff} increased to 39-48 ns in YAG14 and YAG15 with the reduced Ce concentrations of 0.5 and 0.3 %, respectively (Fig. 5b). The fastest decay constant of 27.5 ns was registered in YAG18 with the Ca/Mg ratio of 1:1 and the increased Ce and codopant concentrations – these parameters are very similar to YAG2 with the same $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{Mg}^{2+}$ ratio and the fastest scintillation decay of 26 ns among all the samples studied. However, growth of YAG18 from melt by the Czochralski was more complicated compared to YAG2 as the increased concentrations of the dopants resulted in unstable growth conditions. Light output in all the samples retained over 20000 ph/MeV (Fig. 5a and Table 2).

3.3. Fabrication of 100 mm long scintillation fibers for SPACAL

One of the concepts for detector design at HL-LHC involves spatial calorimeter (SPACAL) comprising inorganic scintillation fibers of 50 and 100 mm in length embedded into a tungsten absorber [3]. Herein, it is important to ensure uniformity of the scintillation parameters along the fibers despite possible variation of the dopant content. Despite the possibility to produce fibers in ready-to-use shape by the micro-pulling-down method [27], mass production of fibers by cutting them from large Czochralski-grown crystals looks more promising. Meanwhile, non-uniform distribution of scintillation parameters along the fibers due to the admixture segregation in the Czochralski growth process may be a serious issue, especially in a YAG:Ce,Ca,Mg compound containing five components. To verify a feasibility to fabricate long fibers with uniform scintillation parameters from Czochralski-grown crystals, a YAG:Ce,Ca,Mg ingot of 20 mm in diameter and 120 mm in length was grown with the same composition as YAG2 crystal. A series of $1 \times 1 \times 100 \text{ mm}^3$ fibers were cut and polished (Fig. 6a), as well as $5 \times 5 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$ samples were fabricated from the top and bottom parts of the boule to control the scintillation parameters. The fibers were completely bleached due to cerium transfer to Ce^{4+} state. No remarkable difference was spotted between top and bottom of the boule – the light output and effective decay time was 22400 ph/MeV, 27.8 ns in the bottom part, and 21850 ph/MeV, 29.3 ns in the upper part, so the

variations did not exceed few hundred ph/MeV and few ns. This demonstrates a feasibility to produce 120 mm long YAG:Ce,Ca,Mg crystals with uniform parameters by the Czochralski method.

Fig. 6. Large YAG:Ce,Ca,Mg crystal and a fragment of 1x1x100 mm³ fiber cut from this ingot (above).

4. Discussion

In contrast to obvious correlation between light output and τ_{eff} in GAGG:Ce,Mg [19] where the scintillation parameters were smoothly controlled by Mg concentration (see Fig. 7), we have not succeeded in reducing the decay time in YAG:Ce,Mg,Ca below 26 ns. Nevertheless, points corresponding to the Ca,Mg-codoped crystals in Fig. 7 are positioned significantly closer to the target area compared to sole Mg- or Ca-doping. Summarizing, the scintillation decay time was reduced by more than twice compared to the Ce³⁺ radiation lifetime, while the loss in light output was just ca. 25%. This certifies that a slow part of the scintillation pulse was effectively quenched, with almost no impact on the number of “prompt” photons.

Fig. 7. Diagram of the correlation between light output and effective decay time in the present and prior works. The area of target values is schematically shown in the lower part of the diagram.

The ways of incorporation of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions into the YAG lattice may stand behind the effect of Ca-Mg synergy. The size factor is the decisive one that determines selective occupation of atoms in a host. Ce^{3+} distribution coefficient in YAG is very low ($k=0.05$ [24]), while no data were found on Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} distribution coefficients. As ionic radii of Ce^{3+} and Ca^{2+} are very similar [28], k (Ca^{2+}) should be very low as well, whereas smaller Mg^{2+} ions should incorporate the lattice more easily. Hence, comparable concentrations of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} in the crystal may be expected in the $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{Mg}^{2+}$ ratio of 3:1 in the melt. Computations of the defect formation energies [29] confirm that large Ca^{2+} cations preferably occupy 8-fold Y^{3+} sites, while smaller Mg^{2+} ions can occupy any cation site (although 4-fold Al^{3+} sites are more preferable [30]), or even interstitial positions at high Mg^{2+} concentration. This means that the selective incorporation of divalent cations into different host sites may be controlled by adjusting Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} concentrations. Following the present perceptions of divalent cation impact on scintillation process in Ce-doped scintillators, $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{Mg}^{2+}$ ions that substitute trivalent host atoms create excessive negative charge in the lattice, which is compensated by Ce^{3+} transfer into tetravalent state [12]. Furthermore, after Ce^{4+} captures

electron and transfers to Ce^{3+} excited state with subsequent emitting of light photon and return to the ground state, Mg^{2+} can trap a hole localized nearby and return cerium back to the Ce^{4+} [13, 14, 17]. Additionally, divalent impurities tend to be placed near oxygen vacancies, forming neutral aggregates [29, 31] and may prevent formation of color centers. The situation with YAG crystals grown in this work under reducing conditions in Ar+CO atmosphere can be even more complicated because of the carbon presence in crystals [24]. Evaluation of defect formation energies in YAG:C [32] and YAG:Ce,C [33] demonstrated that Al^{3+} vacancies and related defects may be also responsible for color center formation and degradation of scintillation performance.

Following the scintillation parameters obtained in this work, a high Mg concentration may promote Mg^{2+} incorporation into interstitials, leading to deterioration of scintillation performance. At the same time, Ca^{2+} -codoping in dodecahedral positions affects more the charged state of neighboring Ce ions (which is manifested in weakening Ce^{3+} absorption bands and rising $\text{Ce}^{4+}\text{-O}^{2-}$ charge transfer absorption in a deep UV). A large ionic radius of Ca^{2+} makes its incorporation as interstitials less probable compared to that of Mg^{2+} , whereas at a high Ca^{2+}/Ce ratios over approximately 3:1 all cerium transfers convert into the tetravalent state. Furthermore, excessive negative charge introduced by $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{RE}^{3+}$ substitution may also create oxygen vacancies, especially at high Ca^{2+} concentrations, resulting in Ce^{3+} luminescence quenching and the appearance of afterglow. Simultaneous codoping with the optimal concentrations of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} enhances scintillation performance by creating proper balance between $\text{Ce}^{3+}/\text{Ce}^{4+}$ [12] and preventing the formation of color centers related to intrinsic and carbon-related defects.

These findings, however, have not provided the decrease of the effective decay constant below 26 ns by increasing Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} contents, in contrast to GAGG:Mg [19]. This is evidently due to different character of Mg^{2+} incorporation in these hosts, namely larger GAGG lattice capacity (the GAGG lattice constant is up to 12.55 Å [34] depending on Ga content) against 12.00 Å in YAG [35] to accommodate this ion into cationic sites, avoiding formation of interstitials. Furthermore, unlike YAG:Ce, one may additionally control thermal ionization in GAGG:Ce by adjusting the energy gap between the Ce^{4+} ground state and the CB edge by $\text{Al}^{3+}/\text{Ga}^{3+}$ substitution. Hence there is a chance to accelerate the luminescence decay in YAG:Ce by substitution of the rare earth cation in the garnet host and/or further adjustment of the codopant concentrations.

5. Conclusions

Dual codoping of YAG:Ce garnet by Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions offers a superior combination of high light output and shorter decay time in YAG:Ce compared to YAG:Ce solely codoped by Ca^{2+} or Mg^{2+} . This effect mirrors the benefits observed in GAGG:Ce,Ca,Mg. A decay time of 26-28 ns achieved in YAG:Ce,Ca,Mg is nearly twice as fast as the intrinsic Ce^{3+} lifetime of 50-60 ns. With a light output of 22800 ph/MeV and a scintillation rise time of 30 ps, this combination yields a CTR of 131 ps. These scintillation parameters are highly promising for particle physics experiments at the HL-LHC in CERN, as well as for next generation of TOF-PET. Furthermore, YAG-based crystals grown from the melt in tungsten crucibles are significantly more cost-efficient than GAGG:Ce crystals, which require expensive iridium crucibles.

Nature of the synergy between Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} dopants in garnet hosts was also explored. By fine-tuning the concentrations of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions, which occupy different crystallographic sites, the incorporation of divalent cations into Y^{3+} and Al^{3+} sublattices, respectively, may be controlled. This codoping impacts the Ce valence state, as well as the charged states of nearby intrinsic and carbon-related defects in the garnet lattice. Remarkably, only approximately 4% of cerium is present in the stable trivalent state, as indicated by the intensity of 4f-5d₁ absorption band of Ce^{3+} in the YAG:Ce,Ca,Mg with the optimized parameters. However, Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} concentrations should be limited to avoid the formation of interstitials, which degrade scintillation performance. Further acceleration of scintillation decay may be achieved by accommodating higher Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} concentrations into the cation sites in the garnet lattice, though this remains a technological challenge. Another promising direction could be bandgap engineering, which involves controlling the thermal ionization from Ce^{4+} 5d levels by adjusting the energy gap between these levels and the bottom of the conductance band at substitution via host cations in YAG:Ce.

A large 120 mm long YAG:Ce,Ca,Mg crystal was successfully grown, and a set of 1x1x100 mm³ fibers were fabricated for testing in SPACAL-W at CERN. The homogeneity of scintillation parameters along the crystal was confirmed by comparing scintillation parameters of the samples fabricated from top and bottom of the ingot, despite possible variations in dopant concentrations.

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Table 2. Compositions and scintillation parameters of the obtained crystals.

Sample no.	Ce, at%	Ca, at%	Mg, at%	Ca/Mg	Ce/Ca+Mg	τ_{rise}	τ_{dec1}	A1	τ_{dec2}	A2	τ_{dec3}	A3	τ_{eff} , ns	Light output, ph MeV ⁻¹
Adjusting Ca/Mg ratio														
YAG:Ce	0.9	-	-	-	-	-	114.57	58.81	251.4	25.96	15.24	159.94	37.3	28900
YAG6	1	-	1	-	1:1	100	4.0	0.00	51.5	51.49	134.7	48.51	73.5	37700
YAG7	1	0.25	1	1:4	1:1	62	2.1	0.46	30.6	34.41	84.8	65.13	47.38	32800
YAG3	1	0.25	0.75	1:3	1:1	91	5.4	1.35	32.3	32.62	86.0	66.02	49.23	33300
YAG1	1	0.5	0.5	1:1	1:1	55	4.9	3.35	31.9	39.70	79.0	56.95	37.75	29200
YAG2	1	0.75	0.25	3:1	1:1	30	2.0	2.30	17.4	24.30	59.0	73.40	26.38	22850
YAG5	1	1	0.25	4:1	1:1.25	60	3.5	3.64	31.5	48.90	76.2	47.46	31.20	28200
YAG:Ce,Ca [18]	1	1	-	-	-	-	55	96	347	4	-	-	57	17500
Adjusting Ce/Ca+Mg ratio														
YAG18	1.5	1.12	0.38	3:1	1:1		3,08	3.19	17.43	21.65	55.33	75.16	27.50	22907
YAG19	1	1	0.25	4:1	1:1.25		3,78	2.83	20.92	24.38	60.10	72.79	32.00	22355
YAG16	1	1	0.33	3:1	1:1.33		3,06	2.36	18.28	20.77	57.78	76.88	30.90	24331
YAG17	1	1.5	0.5	3:1	1:2		3,73	2.57	21.82	25.78	62.69	71.65	33.18	23316
YAG15	0.5	0.75	0.25	3:1	1:2		5,99	3.78	36.06	52,79	93.51	43.43	39.07	22117
YAG14	0.3	0.75	0.25	3:1	1:3		8.06	3.57	45.23	63.67	145.09	32.77	48.17	20489

Graphical Abstract

